

A Journal of the Faculty of Arts
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

THE
INTERNATIONAL
JOURNAL

OF CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH
IN HUMANITIES (INJOCORH)

ISSN 3026-9067

Volume 2 Number 1 2024

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A Critical Analysis of Digital Inclusion and Digital Literacy Development of Learners in the National Open University of Nigeria

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Abstract

Digital literacy (DL) is a multifaceted concept covering many areas of rapidly evolving new technologies which can help to promote active engagement of learners in open-distance learning institution. Though there is a large consensus of DL for future success, literature still reveals lack of digital literacy among learners in higher institutions. The study investigated the influence of access and usage of digital technology as indicators of digital inclusion on digital literacy development of learners. Descriptive survey research design with self-structured questionnaires was used for the study. Samples for the survey were purposive selected from the National Open University of Nigeria, Lagos Study centres. The research questions were analysed and interpreted using means and percentages while Linear Regression Correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. The Will Skill Tool Model was adapted for the theoretical framework of the study. The results showed that there is a strong positive relationship between frequent usage of digital technologies and the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners. The digital technology accessibility and frequent usage of digital technology had a strong positive correlation with the digital literacy proficiency of learners in the study. It is recommended that adequate digital infrastructures and technology should be provided for accessibility and usage to enhance the digital literacy proficiency of learners.

Keywords: Literacy, Digital Literacy, Digital Inclusion, Digital Technology, National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN)

Introduction

University education as the highest level of learning is positioned to provide opportunity for teaching, research and community service. Hence, university education is acknowledged as an optimal contributor to national development through its increasing and specialised programme for the development of highly skilled manpower needed in the different sectors of the nation. The emergence of an open university for Open-Distance Learning (ODL) started with the United Kingdom Open University (UKOU) founded by the Labour Party government in 1969 (Jegede, 2016). Distance education in Nigeria began in the 1930s when Nigerians enrolled in correspondence courses from British universities, providing an alternative for those unable to attend traditional universities. The establishment of the University of Ibadan in 1948, Nigeria's first university, marked the formalisation of distance education programmes. In 1950, the Faculty of Education at the University of Ibadan introduced part-time courses for working adults, signifying the beginning of distance learning within Nigerian universities (Ajayi, 2000). By 1976, the University Senate approved the Department of Adult Education to anchor the programme, which later became the Distance Learning Centre in 2002, offering a range of degree courses (Atolagbe, Umaru, & Oparinde, 2017).

Over time, various institutions adopted distance education under different structures. The University of Lagos established a Correspondence and Open Studies Unit in 1973, which evolved into the Distance Learning Institute in 1997 (Jegede, 2010). A significant milestone was reached in 2002 with the establishment of the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), providing accessible higher education to a broader population, The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) as an open-distance learning

institution was established by the Federal Government of Nigeria as springboard for ODL in 1983 ACT, suspended in 1984 and resuscitated in 2002.

NOUN is the largest single mode tertiary institution in West Africa sub-region positioned to provide opportunities for learners to experience widening access to ensure increase participation in higher education through the open distance learning and e-Learning mode (NOUN Strategic Plan 2013-2017, 2018-2023). It is to enable institutions contribute to the development of Information Communication and Technology (ICT) knowledge and skills based on the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) that is rapidly changing the future of work globally. Although, the Federal Government of Nigeria through the Nigeria Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (NDEPS) document has set a target of achieving 95 per cent digital literacy by 2030. Yet, NOUN as a university with 101, 463 current active learners spread across 103 study centres with 106 programmes and 2,107 courses still operates on a relatively low adoption of digital technologies to support and enhance learning in Nigeria (National Open University of Nigeria Regional Strategy Plan, 2022).

The adoption of a multimodal instructional delivery system by NOUN was based on different digital technologies availability to ensure maximum inclusion of learners. The digital inclusion discourse embraces availability, affordability, accessibility of digital tools, digital literacy skills, and application of relevant online content and services usage to enable participation and collaboration. Digital inclusion is regarded as activities necessary to ensure equitable, meaningful and safe access to design digital technologies and services associated with opportunities for everyone and everywhere (Kalla, 2016). According to Londa Digital Rights and Inclusion in Africa Report 2020 (2021), digital inclusion is regarded as efforts and policies aimed at ensuring all learners and educators regardless of their socioeconomic develop the ability to engage in learning using internet connectivity and digital devices and platforms. While the European Commission views digital inclusion as a way to ensure everyone contributes and benefits from the digital economy and society with underlining pillars of connectivity through broadband, Wi-Fi and mobile devices, with the users capable of using digital devices efficiently and quality of digital services designed to meet individual needs.

As at 2019, 66.7% of the people in Latin America and the Caribbean have access to the Internet. This was due to the integration of technological progress combined with strategies of private or public companies' involvement in the implementation of support and regulatory policies. Recently, the world's population of about 5.3 billion people (66 percent) use the Internet which represents a growth rate of 6.1 percent in 2021 from 5.1 percent in 2020 as shown in Figure 1 below. However, it was 11 per cent at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic for 2019-2020. This indicates 2.7 billion people are offline showing that much needs to be done for the global target of universal and meaningful connectivity for 2030 to be achieved (International Telecommunication Union (ITU), 2020).

Figure 1: Worlds' Population of Internet Use.
 Source: International Technological Union (ITU, 2020)

In the context of National Open University of Nigeria, digital inclusion and digital literacy development are interconnected. Digital inclusion involves ensuring that every learner has access to digital technologies and the Internet which is fundamental for an open university learning environment while digital literacy focuses on the ability to use digital tools and resources effectively (NOUN Regional Strategy Plan, 2022). Globally, UNESCO (2021) gave the report of educational systems during COVID-19 pandemic of about 1.5 billion learners affected resulting in a digital divide gap of inequalities and exclusion; 89% of learners were without access to computers; 82% lacked access to the Internet while 11% did not have mobile networks. Though literature attested to it that NOUN continued with online facilitation and assessment during pandemic. However, learners were not able to access the e-Learning mode as a result of low ICT competence, cost of data, poor internet connectivity and lack of accessibility to digital technologies (NOUN Regional Strategy Plan, 2022).

The implementation of the NOUN regional strategy plan should enable National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) to fulfil its mandate of widening access to higher education by providing opportunities for the acquisition of digital literacy skills and knowledge among learners to impact their different communities positively. Previous studies have established challenges confronting learners during virtual teaching and learning processes; these challenges are due to high cost of bandwidth and low computer literacy level as well as low internet services in most institutions in Nigeria. Although many studies have discussed technology and digital literacy; the practical problem of inadequate access and usage of digital technology through which digital literacy of learners can be enhanced has not been sufficiently addressed, resulting in literature gap. It is upon this backdrop that this study investigates the relationship between accessibility and frequent usage of digital technology and digital literacy proficiency of learners in NOUN.

Objectives of the study

The crux of the study is to investigate the relationship between digital technology accessibility, frequency of usage and digital literacy development of learners in National Open University of Nigeria. Therefore, the objectives are to:

1. examine the extent to which learners have access to digital technologies in the National Open University of Nigeria;
2. explore how learners in the National Open University of Nigeria use digital technologies;
3. investigate the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners in the National Open University of Nigeria;
4. ascertain the relationship between the frequency of usage of digital technologies and the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners in the National Open University of Nigeria; and
5. determine the correlation between the accessibility to digital technologies, the frequency of usage and the level of digital literacy proficiency of learners in National Open University of Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions.

1. To what extent do learners have access to digital technologies in National Open University of Nigeria?
2. How frequent do the learners in National Open University of Nigeria use digital technologies?
3. What is the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners in National Open University of Nigeria?
4. Is there a relationship between the frequency of usage of digital technology and learners' perceived level of digital literacy proficiency?
5. Is there a relationship between accessibility to digital technology, the frequency of usage and digital literacy proficiency of learners?

Hypotheses for the Study

H0₁: There will be no significant relationship between the frequency of usage of digital technologies and the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners in National Open University of Nigeria.

H0₂: There will be no significant correlation between digital technologies accessibility, the frequency of usage and digital literacy proficiency of learners in National Open University of Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework of Will, Skill, Tool Model for Digital Inclusion

The proliferation of digital technology has posed a challenge to the status quo of educational system which led to a paradigm shift in teaching and learning processes (Sasota, Cristobal, Sario, Biyo & Magadia, 2021). The Will, Skill, Tool (WST) model of technology integration postulates that educator's will, skill, and access to technology tools leads to higher stages of classroom technology integration and achievement of learning outcome (Knezek, Christensen, Hancock, & Shoho, 2000). Will is conceptually defined as a positive attitude towards the use of technology in instruction; skill is the self-perceived confidence and readiness to use technology while tool is described as the accessibility to technology tools and infrastructure (Ofori-Atta, Osei-Poku & Osei, 2022). Sasota et al., (2021) established will as willingness towards computer usage, skill for technology competence and tool for access to digital technology to indicate effective integration of ICT in teaching and learning environment. The WST model can serve as a guide to enlighten facilitator on how to integrate ICT in a virtual learning environment. Knezek et al. (2000) asserted that skill is the major predictor of ICT integration in teaching and learning. Tool is described as the access to technology tools and infrastructure. Ofori-Atta, Osei-Poku & Osei, (2022) was of the opinion that the will and the skill alone are not enough for the integration of technology to achieve the expected learning outcome without the availability of technology tools. In addition, his findings revealed that the parameters of the Will, Skill, and Tool Model help to predict technology integration in the classroom.

Figure 2: The WST Model

Source: Researcher, 2023

Previous studies have limited the use of WST model to the integration of technology. The WST conceptual model in Figure 2 above is adapted for the study to show that WILL, SKILL, TOOL can be used for the independent variables of digital inclusion with the digital literacy proficiency as dependent variable. Willingness for the usage of digital technology, Skill for digital literacy proficiency and Tool as access to digital tools which are prerequisites for the digital literacy development of learners. The findings in this study revealed that digital technology accessibility and the usage of digital technology had a strong positive correlation with the digital literacy proficiency of learners having $R=.795$. Hence, the adjusted R square value of .621 indicated that the digital technology accessibility and the usage of digital technologies jointly contributed 62.1% to the variability of digital literacy proficiency of learners. This implies that, for every small change in digital technology accessibility and the usage of digital technology, there is a 62.1% change in the digital literacy proficiency of learners. The implication is that Will, Skill, Tool indicator of digital inclusion is a predictor of digital literacy development of learners. Previous studies have

established that Will (attitude towards computer), Skill (technology competency), and Tool (access to technology tools) are all essential ingredients for a teacher to effectively integrate ICT in teaching. Knezek et al. (2003) collected data from 1999 to 2001 and it was found out that 70–84% of teachers’ ability to integrate technology during teaching could be predicted by Will, Skill, and Tool model. Also, Morales et al. (2005) studied 10 teachers as samples from 2001 to 2005 and discovered that Will, Skill, and Tool accounted for 64–83% of the variance in technology integration proficiency for practicing teachers.

Methodology

The study adopted the quantitative research approach and questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The population for the study were learners in two selected National Open University Nigeria in Lagos: Mushin and Lagos Mainland Study Centres. Convenience sampling technique was used to select the respondents. Ninety questionnaires were administered while seventy-one copies of the questionnaires were filled correctly. The self-structured questionnaire had Section A for the collection of demographic information from the respondents; Section B for data collection on the accessibility to digital technologies and Section C for the frequency of usage of digital technologies using 4 Likert Scale of agreement. Section D of the questionnaire was adopted from Dip. Com 2.1 digital literacy proficiency which was divided into five sub-sections with three items each on a four-point proficiency scale measurement. The reliability of the research instrument was done using test-retest method and reliability coefficient of 0.832 was obtained which was considered adequate based on George and Mallery’s (2003) rule that states the rule of thumb for the acceptance and rejection of reliability data as follows: $\alpha \geq 0.9$ = Excellent (High-stake testing), $0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.9$ = Good (Low-stakes testing), $0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$ = Acceptable, $0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$ = poor, < 0.5 = unacceptable. The data analysis was done with SPSS version 21 descriptively using Mean, percentages and standard deviation. The data was personally collected through the direct administration of the self-structured questionnaires to the learners in Lagos Mainland Study centre and Mushin Study Centre. The frequency count and percentage were used to analyse the data collected for the demographic information and to answer the research questions. Simple Linear Regression Analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance to ensure the clarity of the findings.

Findings and Results Analysis

The quantitative data obtained from the field was analysed using Statistical Package for Service Solution (SPSS) version 25. It is worthy of note that out of the 75 copies of the questionnaire sent out, 94.7% were correctly filled and used for the analysis. The descriptive analysis used percentages and mean to determine the opinion of the participants based on a 4-point Likert Scale to answer the research questions. The section D of the questionnaire was adapted from National Digital Literacy Framework (NDLF, 2021) based on European Commission’s Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp 2.2). Hence, the decision rule 1-2= Foundation; 3-4= Intermediate; 5-6= Advanced; 7-8= Highly Specialised was used for rating the proficiency level of digital literacy according to the National Digital Literacy Framework (NDLF, 2021). The decision rule for the research question 1 and 2 on the item statements is taken to be 8.00 value divided by 4 Likert Scale therefore the Grand Mean for the research is taken to be equal to, or greater than 2.00. Therefore, respondents’ options were based on Points Boundary Limit as follows: Always (3.50–5.00); Sometimes (2.50–3.49); Rarely (1.50–2.49); Never (0.50–1.49).

Demographic Information of the Participants

Table 1: Bio-data of Respondents

Name of Institutions	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lagos Mainland Study Centre	45	63.4
Mushin Study Centre	26	36.6
Total	71	100
Gender of the Respondents		
Male	26	36.6

Female	45	63.4
Total	71	100.0
Age of the Respondents		
16-20yrs	8	11.3
21-30yrs	22	31.0
31yrs and above	41	57.7
Total	71	100.0
Level		
300 Level	22	31.0
400 Level	14	19.7
500 Level	35	49.3
Total	71	100.0
Departments of Respondents		
Business Education	21	29.6
Others	50	70.4
Total	71	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Information on Table 1 reveals that 45 (63.4%) of the total respondents were in Lagos Mainland Study Centre while 26 (36.6%) respondents were in Mushin Study Centre of National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). This implies that most of the respondents were in Lagos Mainland Study centre. The table also shows that 26 (36.6%) of the respondents were male while 45 (63.4%) were female. Similarly, 8 of the respondents that represent 11.3% are within the age range of 16-20yrs, 22 (31%) fall within the age range of 21-30yrs, and 41 of the respondents which stand for 57.7% are within the age range of 31yrs and above. This indicates that the majority of the respondents were within the age range of 31yrs and above. Furthermore, 22 (31.0%) respondents were in 300 level, 14 (19.7%) in 400 level and 35 (49%) in 500 level. This shows that the respondents were in 300, 400 and 500 levels. Finally, 21 (29.6%) of the respondents are in the Department of Business Education and 51 (70.4%) respondents are in other departments.

Research Question 1: To what extent do you have access to digital tools for learning? The mean rating is as follows: Keys: Never (N) Daily (D) Weekly (W) Monthly (M).

Table 2: Respondents' Responses on how would you rate your accessibility to the following digital tools? (N=71).

SN	Items	Never	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	\bar{X}
1.	Computers or laptops or smartphones	8 (11.3%)	35 (49.3%)	21 (29.6%)	7 (9.9%)	2.42
2.	Wi-Fi&Broadband Model for internet connectivity	7 (9.9%)	44 (62.0%)	20 (28.2%)	0 (0.0%)	2.44
3.	Electronic mail e.g. Google, Yahoo	7 (9.9%)	51 (71.8%)	7 (9.9%)	6 (8.5%)	2.42
4.	Projector for PowerPoint Presentation	7 (9.9%)	44 (62.0%)	13 (18.3%)	7 (9.9%)	2.25
5.	Social Media such as WhatsApp, YouTube, Zoom	6 (8.5%)	44 (62.0%)	7 (9.9%)	14 (19.7%)	2.52
6.	Learning Management Systems LMS	0 (0.0%)	43 (60.6%)	22 (31.0%)	6 (8.5%)	2.21
Grand mean						2.52

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 shows the mean of each item based on the opinion of the respondents regarding the extent of the accessibility of digital technologies. The result shows that items 1 to 6 have mean scores of 2.42, 2.44, 2.42, 2.25, 2.52 and 2.21 respectively which indicate high extent of accessibility. Generally, the grand mean for the construct reveals 2.52 indicating the majority of the respondents agreed on the accessibility of digital technologies. The result shows that the daily access to social media has a higher frequency and percentage, followed by the Wi-Fi and broadband internet connectivity with the mean score of 2.42 and email having the same frequency of 2.42 when compared with weekly and monthly accessibility. The implication is that the respondents agreed they have access to digital technologies on a daily basis. Though the Digital Global Overview (2020) reported that about 60% of people from Nigeria do not have access to the Internet; the study indicated that accessibility to internet connectivity for learning has improved over the years.

Research Question 2: What is the frequent usage of digital technologies for learning by learners? The mean rating is as follows: Keys: Never (N) Rarely (R) Sometimes (S) Always (A).

Table 3: Respondents' Responses on the frequent usage of digital technologies (N=71)

SN	Items	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Always	\bar{X}
1.	Computers or laptops or smartphones	6 (8.5%)	29 (40.8%)	7 (9.9%)	29 (40.8%)	2.83
2.	Wi Fi & Broadband Model for internet connectivity	9 (12.7%)	20 (28.2%)	0 (0.0%)	42 (59.2%)	3.34
3.	Electronic mail e.g. Google, Yahoo	8 (11.3%)	7 (9.9%)	7 (9.9%)	49 (69.0%)	3.37
4.	Projector for PowerPoint Presentation	6 (8.5%)	8 (11.3%)	35 (49.3%)	22 (31.0%)	3.03
5.	Social Network such as WhatsApp, YouTube, Zoom	6 (8.5%)	8 (11.3%)	49 (69.0%)	8 (11.3%)	2.83
6.	Learning Management Systems	7 (9.9%)	9 (12.7%)	20 (28.2%)	35 (49.3%)	3.17
Grand Mean						2.98

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3 reveals the mean of each item on the opinion of respondents on their frequency of usage of digital technologies. The result shows that items 1 to 6 have mean scores of 2.83, 3.34, 3.37, 3.03, 2.83 and 3.17 respectively. This indicates a high frequency of usage. The grand mean for the construct is 2.98 which implies that the majority of the respondents use digital technologies always. Kyari, Adiuku-Brown, Abechi & Adedokun's (2018) findings confirmed the fact that innovative of technology is very much conditioned by the level of digital skills of the people which indicates strong correlation between skills and use of digital technologies.

Research Question 3: What is the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners? The mean rating is as follows Key: Foundation (F), Intermediate (I), Advanced (A) Highly Specialised (HS).

Table 4: Respondents' Responses on level of digital literacy proficiency of learners (N=71).

SN	Information and data literacy	F	I	A	HS	\bar{X}
1.	I can search for information, retrieve and store information in digital environments	8 (11.3%)	6 (8.5%)	14 (19.7%)	45 (60.6%)	3.30
2.	I can analyse, compare and critically evaluate the credibility and reliability of sources of information and digital content.	7 (9.9%)	6 (8.5%)	14 (19.7%)	44 (62.0%)	3.34
3.	I can organise, store and retrieve data, information and content in digital environments.	8 (11.3%)	13 (18.3%)	7 (9.9%)	43 (60.6%)	3.20
Grand Mean						3.28

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4 shows the mean score of each item in the opinion of respondents regarding information and data literacy. The result shows that items 1 to 3 have mean scores of 3.30, 3.34 and 3.20 respectively indicating high perceived level of digital literacy proficiency. Generally, the grand mean for the construct reveals 3.28; this shows that the majority of the respondents have knowledge of information and data literacy. Information and data literacy is shown to be the most developed digital literacy proficiency among the learners. Information and data literacy, according to Law, Woo, de la Torre and Wong (2018), is regarded as the most important digital literacy competence which includes ability to browse and search for information online as well as managing and evaluating accessed information.

Table 5: Respondents' Responses on the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners (N=71).

SN	Communication and Collaboration	F	I	A	HS	\bar{X}
1.	I can interact through a variety of digital technologies and understand appropriate digital communication means for a given context.	7 (9.9%)	8 (11.3%)	48 (67.6%)	8 (11.3%)	2.80
2.	I can share data, information and digital content with others through appropriate digital technologies.	7 (9.9%)	8 (11.3%)	48 (67.6%)	8 (11.3%)	2.80
3.	I can participate in society using public and private digital services as participatory citizenship through appropriate digital technologies.	7 (9.9%)	7 (9.9%)	42 (59.2%)	15 (21.1%)	2.92
4.	I can use digital tools and technologies for collaborative processes and co-creation of resources.	7 (9.9%)	8 (11.3%)	42 (59.2%)	14 (19.7%)	2.89
Grand Mean						2.85

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 5 shows the mean score of each item in the opinion of respondents regarding communication and collaboration. The result shows that items 4 to 7 have mean scores of 2.80, 2.80, 2.92 and 2.89 respectively; this indicates a level of agreement to the statements. Generally, the grand mean for the construct is 2.85, indicating that the majority of the respondents have knowledge about communication and collaboration for interaction and sharing of knowledge through digital technologies. Doh, Rhim & Lee, (2016)

ascertained the importance of communication and collaboration between learners and facilitators in virtual learning environment.

Table 6: Respondents' Responses on perceived level digital literacy proficiency of learners. (N=71).

SN	Digital content creation	F	I	A	HS	\bar{X}
1.	I can create and edit digital content in different formats, express myself through digital technologies.	15 (21.1%)	6 (8.5%)	7 (9.9%)	43 (59.2%)	3.10
2.	I can modify,improve and integrate information and content into existing body of knowledge.	8 (11.3%)	7 (9.9%)	13 (18.3%)	43 (59.2%)	3.28
3.	I understand how copyright and license apply to data, information and digital content.	8 (11.3%)	6 (8.5%)	43 (59.2%)	14 (19.7%)	2.89
Grand Mean						3.09

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 6 reveals the mean score of each item in the opinion of respondents on the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners about digital content creation. The result shows that items 8 to 10 have mean scores of 3.10, 3.28 and 2.89 respectively with a grand mean score of 3.09; this implies that the majority of the respondents perceived that they have high proficiency in digital literacy. The result shows that the respondents have developed proficiency in digital content creation.

Table 7: Respondents' Responses on their perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners (N=71).

SN	Safety	F	I	A	HS	\bar{X}
1.	I can protect devices and digital content understand risk and threats in digital environments.	8 (11.3%)	6 (8.5%)	43 (60.6%)	14 (19.7%)	2.89
2.	I can protect personal data and privacy in digital environments, how to use and share personal information based on privacy policy.	7 (9.9%)	8 (11.3%)	14 (19.7%)	42 (59.2%)	2.89
3.	I am aware of health-risks and threats to physical well-being as well as cyber bullying if digital environments.	8 (11.3%)	7 (9.9%)	42 (59.2%)	14 (19.7%)	2.87
Grand Mean						2.88

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 7 itemises the mean score of each item on the opinion of respondents regarding safety and security. The result shows that items 11 to 13 have mean scores of 2.89, 2.89 and 2.87 respectively with 2.88 as the grand mean score; this indicates a level of agreement to the statements. Generally, the construct shows that the majority of the respondents have knowledge of safety needed for digital technology use.

Table 8: Respondents' Responses on the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners (N=71).

No	Problem-solving	F	I	A	HS	\bar{X}
1.	I can solve simple technical problems when operating digital devices.	8 (11.3%)	7 (9.9%)	42 (59.2%)	14 (19.7%)	2.87
2.	I can assess personal information needs by identifying, evaluating, selecting and use of digital tools.	6 (8.5%)	8 (11.3%)	43 (59.2%)	14 (19.7%)	2.92
3.	I understand digital literacy needed for self-development and be able to support others with their digital literacy development,	7 (9.9%)	7 (9.9%)	42 (59.2%)	15 (21.1%)	2.92
Grand Mean						2.90

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 8 reveals the mean score of each item on the opinion of respondents on the perceived digital literacy proficiency. The items 14 to 16 have mean scores of 2.87, 2.92 and 2.92 respectively with 2.90 as the grand mean score for the construct. This shows that the majority of the respondents agreed to the above statements. In digital literacy, learners are expected to develop effective learning skills to study in rich digital environments. The findings of Fields & Hartnett (2018) corroborate the result that student's exhibit digital fluency to utilise digital technologies for problem-solving purposes.

Hypothesis One

HO₁- There is no significant correlation between the frequency of usage of digital technologies and the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners in National Open University of Nigeria.

Table 9: Relationship between frequent usage of digital technologies and level of digital literacy proficiency of learners

Variable	Mean	SD	N	Df	r*	P	Remark	Decision
Frequency of usage	3.10	.564	71	69	.787**	0.00	Sig.	Reject HO ₁
	3.04	.531						

level of DLP

p<0.05

The correlation coefficient is .787**. This implies that there is a strong positive relationship between the frequency of usage of digital technologies and the perceived level of digital literacy proficiency of learners. Since the *p-value* .000 is less than the level of significance of 0.05 ($p<0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternate hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the frequency of usage of digital technologies and the level of digital literacy proficiency of learners.

Hypothesis Two

HO₂- There will be no significant relationship between digital technology accessibility, the usage of digital technologies, and digital literacy proficiency of learners in National Open University of Nigeria.

Table 10: Linear Regression Analysis Results of Joint Contribution of Digital Technologies Accessibility and Usage of Digital Technologies, and Digital Literacy Proficiency of Learners.

Model summary $R = .795^a$ $R^2 = .632$ R^2 (Adjusted) = .621 Standard Error of Estimate = .327

$F = 58.324, P < 0.005$

Model		Unstandardised		Standardised	T	p.	Remarks
		Coefficients		Coefficients			
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.105	.317		3.482	.000	
	Accessibility of DI	-.187	.120	-.120	-1.555	.125	Not. Sig.
	Frequency of usage	.776	.073	.824	10.643	.000	Significant

a. Predictors: (Constant), FoU & AoDI

b. Dependent Variable: Proficiency levels of learners

The result from Table 10 reveals that digital technology accessibility and the usage of digital technology had a strong positive correlation with the digital literacy proficiency of learners ($R = .795$). Since it is a joint contribution, the adjusted R square value will be used because it is not influenced by additional variables. Hence, the adjusted R square value of .621 indicated that the digital technology accessibility and the usage of digital technologies jointly contributed 62.1% to the variability of digital literacy proficiency of learners. This implies that, for every small change in digital technology accessibility and the usage of digital technology, there is a 62.1% change in the digital literacy proficiency of learners. The hypothesis testing for the frequency of usage of digital technologies showed a correlation coefficient of .776. Hence, there is a fair positive relationship between accessibility to digital technologies and the frequency of usage of digital technologies. This implies that there is a significant correlation between accessibility to digital technologies and the frequency of usage of digital technologies among learners in National Open University of Nigeria.

Conclusion

Globally, ensuring digital inclusion has become a potential and essential tool for promoting a better learning environment for learners in open universities. The study reveals that accessibility to digital technologies has the probability to influence the frequency of usage of digital technology. Also, results from the study shows that widening access to digital tools would indirectly influence the usage as well as promote digital literacy development of learners. The study therefore suggests that learners should be exposed to frequent usage of digital technology which will significantly influence digital literacy development of learners. Also, the findings suggest that for the level of digital literacy proficiency of learners to improve, digital inclusion initiatives should be at the front line of the institution governing body and stakeholders' decision as an input of learning process, procedure and delivery method for full benefits.

Recommendations

All the relevant stakeholders in education system, information technology, government parastatals as well as private and non-governmental organisations should work together to achieve the objective of the national digital literacy framework and standard. This is to help equip Nigerians with digital literacy skills, to enable them prepare for opportunities that will open up within and beyond the shores of the country. This effort will promote diversification of the country's economy, significantly reduce unemployment and then enhance labour productivity and exportation.

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